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**STRATEGIES FOR INITIAL PUBLIC OFFER (IPO) –
A STUDY ON THE SUCCESS AND FAILURE**

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ABSTRACT

Going public is, in many cases, a step towards the eventual separation of ownership and control. Ownership matters for the effects it can have on management's incentives to make optimal operating and investment decisions. In particular, where the separation of ownership and control is incomplete, an agency problem between non-managing and managing shareholders can arise rather than maximizing expected shareholder value, managers may maximize the expected private utility of their control benefits (say, perquisite consumption) at the expense of outside shareholders. Most companies that go public do so via an initial public offering of shares (IPO) to investors. New issues of existing companies are, by and large, very good investments. They provide an opportunity for acquiring shares in ongoing profit-making companies at relatively low prices. On the other hand, all new issues of newly formed companies are not good investments.

One good thing about the IPO market vis-à-vis the earlier times has been that most of them have been from good companies and at reasonable prices. This trend, however, seems to be narrowing off and we are increasingly seeing public issues from the relatively not-so-good or known companies and at fairly stretched prices.

Therefore, it becomes necessary for the investors to become cautious and be more selective about their investments in IPOs.

The present paper examines the issues and challenges confronted the IPO. It tries to find out the strategies to IPO for investors and companies. The paper assesses the success or failure of IPO and takes into account the assessment of IPO norms and IPO grading.

KEYWORDS: *Initial public offering, IPO grading, primary capital market, investors.*

INTRODUCTION

Small companies are becoming big. They have devised novel ways to raise funds, fast, to realize inspirational growth. From the various options available, IPOs remain the hot favourite for Indian companies. The first public offer of securities by a company after its inception is known as Initial Public Offer (IPO). Going public is a process by which a business owned by one or several individuals is converted in to a business owned by many. It involves the offer of part ownership of the company to the public through the sale of equity securities (stock).

IPO dilutes the ownership stake and diffuses corporate control as it provides ownership to investors in the form of equity shares. It can be used as exit strategy and finance strategy. As a financing strategy, its main purpose is to raise funds for the company. When used as an exit strategy, existing investors can offload equity holdings to the public. Apparently, for Indian companies, IPOs remain a hot favourite to raise funds. The model of IPOs is tried and tested by companies in various sectors. IPOs can be a risky investment. For the individual investor, it is tough to predict what the stock will do on its initial day of trading and in the near future because there is often little historical data with which to analyze the company. Also, most IPOs are of companies going through a transitory growth period, which are subject to additional uncertainty regarding their future values.

IPOs are the first offer of shares to the public. The emphasis is on

- shares,
- an offer to the wide public (otherwise it would be a private placement) and
- the first time that shares would be offered

REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

Going public is, in many cases, a step towards the eventual separation of ownership and control. Ownership matters for the effects it can have on management's incentives to make optimal operating and investment decisions. In particular, where the separation of ownership and control is incomplete, an agency problem between non-managing and managing shareholders can arise (Jensen and Meckling (1976)): rather than maximizing expected shareholder value, managers

may maximize the expected private utility of their control benefits (say, perquisite consumption) at the expense of outside shareholders. Most companies that go public do so via an initial public offering of shares to investors. IPOs have interested financial economists for many decades. Early writers, notably Logue (1973) and Ibbotson (1975), documented that when companies go public, the shares they sell tend to be under priced, in that the share price jumps substantially on the first day of trading. Since the 1960s, this ‘under pricing discount’ has averaged around 19% in the United States, suggesting that firms leave considerable amounts of money on the table. Under pricing has tended to fluctuate a great deal, averaging 21% in the 1960s, 12% in the 1970s, 16% in the 1980s, 21% in the 1990s, and 40% in the four years since 2000 (reflecting mostly the tail-end of the late 1990s internet boom). Clearly, under pricing is costly to a firm’s owners: shares sold for personal account are sold at too low a price, while the value of shares retained after the IPO is diluted. In dollar terms, IPO firms appear to leave many billions ‘on the table’ every year in the U.S. IPO market alone. Levis (1990) conducts a similar analysis for the U.K. Though now no longer in regular use, the preferred IPO method in the U.K. until the early 1990s was the ‘offer for sale’, which required that allocations be pro-rated in the event of over-subscription. The unconditional average degree of under pricing for the 123 IPOs in Levis’ sample is 8.6%, but this declines to 5.14% or less for medium-sized and small applications conditional on being allocated stock. Thus while rationing reduces the initial returns among small investors, it does not drive them down to zero. Keloharju (1993) provides similar evidence for Finland, though he also shows that investors placing large orders lose money on an allocation-weighted basis. In Israel, this latter finding seems to hold true more generally: uninformed IPO investors do not appear to break even at all. Amihud, Hauser, and Kirsh (2003) find that uninformed investors earned a negative allocation-weighted initial return in Israel in the early 1990s, of -1.2% on average.

Behavioral finance is interested in the effect on stock prices of ‘irrational’ or ‘sentiment’ investors. The potential for such an effect would seem particularly large in the case of IPOs, since IPO firms are young, immature, and relatively informational opaque and hence hard to value. The first paper to model an IPO company’s optimal response to the presence of sentiment investors is Ljungqvist, Nanda, and Singh (2004). They assume some sentiment investors hold optimistic beliefs about the future prospects for the IPO issue company. The issuer’s objective is to capture as much of the ‘surplus’ under the sentiment investors’ downward-sloping demand curve as possible, that is, to maximize the excess valuation over the fundamental value of the stock. Flooding the market with stock will depress the price, so the optimal strategy involves holding back stock in inventory to keep the price from falling. Eventually, nature reveals the true value of the stock and the price reverts to fundamental value. That is, in the long-run IPO returns are negative, consistent with the empirical evidence in Ritter (1991) and others. This assumes the existence of short sale constraints, or else arbitrageurs would trade in such a way that prices reflected fundamental value even in the short term. Aggarwal (2008) analyzes the Indian IPO issue and their pricing mechanism with empirical studies on the valuation of IPOs and both theoretical and empirical work on the determinants of short-run under pricing. Aggarwal, Krigman and Womack (2002), Madhusoodanan, and Thiripalraju (1997) and Rock (1986) and Jegadeesh, Weinstein, and Welch (1993), amongst others have reviewed the problem of underpricing. Lowry and Schwert (2000) analyzed the aggregate IPO market activity and also have examined the initial returns at the firm level. The research also studies strong cycles in the number of IPOs by calculating the average initial returns realized by investors from 1960 to

1997. The statistical measures being used in the study are mean, median, standard deviation and auto-correlations. The results show that IPOs cycles occurs and has subsequent effect on returns and underperformance. The study also shows that clustering of IPOs happens in the market and is also associated with predictably different initial returns. And also the information about the value of an IPO which is being available during registration period has an effect on the prices and offering decisions of other firms.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research in common parlance refers to a search for knowledge. One can also define research as a scientific and systematic search for pertinent information on a specific topic. The present study has been undertaken to examine the issues and challenges to be addressed by means of initial public offer.

The present paper aims to achieve the following objectives:

- To examine the issues and challenges confronted the IPO;
- To find out the strategies to IPO for investors and companies
- To assess the success or failure of IPO
- To assess IPO norms and IPO grading.

AREA OF STUDY

The paper is not confined to any particular area; on the other hand it is applicable to whole India. However, opinion of officers/managers of various share broking companies in Jaipur and Moradabad district of Rajasthan and Uttar Pradesh respectively has been taken about the growth, roadblocks and benefits of IPO. Their views have been incorporated in this paper. The paper also takes the references of various articles written by various experts on IPO.

We have used qualitative research techniques as focus group discussion with respect to IPO in various share broking companies. Our focus group discussion was based on some share broking companies in region of Jaipur and Moradabad district. The discussions were based on key analysis of primary market with emphasis on IPO.

GROWTH OF IPO MARKET IN INDIA

Year	No. of IPOs	Amount (Rs. In Crore)
1991-1992	158	724
1992-1993	467	3673
1993-1994	693	7650

1994-1995	1231	9919
1995-1996	1357	10924.11
1996-1997	717	5958.60
1997-1998	52	1047.52
1998-1999	18	404.21
1999-2000	51	2719.04
2000-2001	114	2722.38
2001-2002	7	1201.8
2002-2003	6	1038.68
2003-2004	14	1412
2004-2005	23	12382
2005-2006	79	10936
2006-2007	77	28504
2007-2008	85	42595
2008	37	18393
2009	20	19266
2010	67	38000
2011	38	14112

Source: SEBI Annual Reports and Economic Survey Report

IPO MARKET IN 2010

The higher valuations in the secondary market during 2010 have boosted the primary market sentiment. The number of FPOs has been declining over the years perhaps because they involve a further reduction in the government's stake in public sector enterprises. Besides, most of the successful public offers in recent times have been by cash-rich government companies that are under fewer compulsions to tap the capital market at frequent intervals. Another interesting feature is the preponderance of large-sized public issues. There were as many as 13 issues of over Rs.1,000 crore and only nine issues of less than Rs.50 crore. The large average size of the public offer reinforces the point that the new issues market has not been able to accommodate

small and medium enterprises. Hence the quest for a separate, dedicated exchange for them will continue.

IPOS IN 2009 AND 2010

S. No	Company Name	Offer Price (Rs.)	Current Price (Rs) as on 20.07.2012	% Change (+/-)	Issue Dates	Closing Date
1	Adani Power Ltd.	100	45.45	-54.55	28.07.09	31.07.09
2	Aqua Logistics	220	11.4	-94.82	25.01.10	28.01.10
3	ARSS Infrastructure Projects	450	42.85	-90.48	08.02.10	11.02.10
4	Ashoka Buildcon Ltd.	324	210	-35.19	24.09.10	28.09.10
5	Astec Lifesciences	82	25.9	-68.41	29.10.10	04.11.09
6	Aster Silicates Ltd.	118	7.9	-93.31	24.06.10	28.06.10
7	A2Z Maintenance and Engineering Services Ltd.	400	91.7	-77.08	08.12.10	10.12.10
8	Bajaj Corp	660	132.1	-79.98	02.08.10	05.08.10
9	Bedmutha Industries Ltd.	102	14	-86.27	28.09.10	01.10.10
10	Birla Shloka Edutech	50	6.75	-86.50	11.01.10	13.01.10
11	BS Transcomm Ltd.	248	188.4	-24.03	06.01.11	08.10.10
12	C Mahindra Exports Ltd.	110	99.45	-9.59	31.12.10	06.01.11

13	Cantabil Retail India Ltd	135	21.85	-83.81	22.09.10	27.09.10
14	Career Point Infosystems Ltd.	310	152.35	-50.85	16.09.10	21.09.10
15	Claris Lifesciences Limited	228	174.15	-23.62	24.11.10	02.12.10
16	Coal India Ltd.	245	361	47.35	18.10.10	21.10.10
17	Commercial Engineers & Body Builders Co.Ltd.	127	86.25	-32.09	30.09.10	05.10.10
18	Cox and Kings (India)	330	129.35	-60.80	18.11.09	20.11.09
19	DB Reality Ltd	468	79.2	-83.08	29.01.10	02.02.10
20	DB Corp Ltd	212	202.2	-4.62	11.12.09	15.12.09
21	Den Networks Ltd	195	122.85	-37.00	28.10.09	30.10.09
22	DQ Entertainment International	80	23.65	-70.44	08.03.10	10.03.10
23	Electrosteel Integrated Ltd.	11	5.95	-45.91	21.09.10	24.09.10
24	Emmbi Polyarns	45	11.8	-73.78	01.02.10	03.02.10
25	Eros International Media Ltd.	175	172.75	-1.29	17.09.10	21.09.10
26	Euro Multivision	75	5.35	-92.87	22.09.09	24.09.09
27	Excel Infoways	85	25.1	-70.47	14.07.09	17.07.09

28	Gallantt Ispat Ltd.	50	20.35	-59.30	22.09.10	24.09.10
29	Globus Spirits	100	109.65	9.65	31.08.09	02.09.09
30	Godrej Properties	490	513.8	4.86	09.12.09	11.12.09
31	Goenka Diamond & Jewels	135	189.05	40.04	23.03.10	26.03.10
32	Gujarat Pipavav Port Ltd.	46	56.6	23.04	23.08.10	26.08.10
33	Gravita India Ltd.	125	181	44.80	01.11.10	03.11.10
34	Gyscoal Alloys Ltd	71	11.25	-84.15	13.10.10	15.10.10
35	Hathway Cable & Datacom	240	198.05	-17.48	09.02.10	11.02.10
36	Hindustan Media Ventures	166	117.15	-29.43	05.07.10	07.07.10
37	IL & FS Transport Networks	258	179.05	-30.60	11.03.10	15.03.10
38	Indiabulls Power	45	13.5	-70.00	12.10.09	15.10.09
39	Indosolar Ltd.	29	4.8	-83.45	13.09.10	15.09.10
40	Infinite Computer Solution India	165	119.15	-27.79	11.01.10	13.01.10
41	Intrasoft Technologies	145	52	-64.14	23.03.10	26.03.10
42	Jaypee Infratech Ltd.	102	57.45	-43.68	29.04.10	04.05.10
43	Jindal Cotex Ltd	75	53.3	-28.93	27.08.09	01.09.09

44	JSW Energy Ltd	100	53.15	-46.85	07.12.09	09.12.09
45	Jubilant Foodworks	145	1263.4	771.31	18.01.10	20.01.10
46	Mahindra Holidays & Resorts	300	299.05	-0.32	23.06.09	26.06.09
47	Man Infraconstruction	252	213.6	-15.24	18.02.10	22.02.10
48	Mandhana Industries	130	234	80.00	27.04.10	29.04.10
49	Manganese Ore India Ltd	375	278.05	-25.85	26.11.10	01.12.10
50	MBL Infrastructures	180	179.1	-0.50	27.11.09	01.12.09
51	Microsec Financial Services Ltd.	118	28.35	-75.97	21.09.10	21.09.10
52	Midfield Industries Ltd.	133	39.15	-70.56	21.07.10	21.07.10
53	NHPC Ltd	36	18.45	-48.75	12.08.09	12.08.09
54	Nitesh Estates Ltd.	54	13.9	-74.26	27.04.10	27.04.10
55	NMDC Ltd	300	191.05	-36.32	10.03.10	12.03.10
56	NTPC Ltd.	201	155.9	-22.44	03.02.10	05.02.10
57	Oberoi Realty	260	235.15	-9.56	06.10.10	08.10.10
58	Oil India Ltd	1050	496.3	-52.73	07.09.09	10.09.09
59	Orient Green Power Company Ltd.	47	10.45	-77.77	21.09.10	24.09.10
60	Punjab & Sind Bank	120	68.1	-43.25	13.12.10	16.12.10

61	Parabolic Drugs Ltd.	75	23.05	-69.27	14.06.10	17.06.10
62	Persistent Systems Ltd.	310	399.4	28.84	17.03.10	19.03.10
63	Pipavav Defence & Offshore Engineering Company Ltd	58	79.9	37.76	16.09.09	18.09.09
64	Pradip Overseas	110	87.4	-20.55	11.03.10	15.03.10
65	Prakash Steelage Ltd.	110	160.05	45.50	05.08.10	10.08.10
66	Prestige Estates Projects Ltd.	183	108.55	-40.68	12.10.10	14.10.10
67	Ramky Infrastructure Ltd.	450	111	-75.33	21.09.10	23.09.10
68	Ravikumar Distilleries Ltd	64	10.15	-84.14	08.12.10	10.12.10
69	Rishabhdev Technocable	33	3.05	-90.76	04.06.09	09.06.09
70	RPP Infra Projects Ltd.	75	53.35	-28.87	18.11.10	22.11.10
71	Rural Electrification Corporation	203	191.55	-5.64	19.02.08	22.02.08
72	Sea TV Network Ltd.	100	54.75	-45.25	27.09.10	29.09.10
73	Shekhawati Poly-Yarn Ltd.	30	43.7	45.67	27.12.10	29.12.10

74	Shree Jewellery Ltd.	Ganesh House	260	107.25	-58.75	19.03.10	23.03.10
75	SJVN Ltd.		26	20.25	-22.12	29.04.10	03.05.10
76	SKS Microfinance Ltd.		985	90.55	-90.81	28.07.10	02.08.10
77	Syncom Healthcare		75	10.35	-86.20	27.01.10	29.01.10
78	Talwalkars Value Fitness Ltd.	Better	128	172.3	34.61	21.04.10	23.04.10
79	Tarapur Transformers		75	13.35	-82.20	26.04.10	28.04.10
80	Technofab Engineering		240	134.05	-44.15	29.06.10	02.07.10
81	Techpro Systems Ltd.		355	154.45	-56.49	23.09.10	28.09.10
82	Texmo Pipes and Products		90	12	-86.67	16.02.10	19.02.10
83	Thangamayil Jewellery		75	181.95	142.60	27.01.10	29.01.10
84	Thinksoft Services	Global	125	70.9	-43.28	22.09.09	01.10.09
85	United Bank of India		66	58.8	-10.91	23.02.10	25.02.10
86	VA Tech Wabag Ltd.		1310	498.15	-61.97	22.09.10	27.09.10
87	Vascon Engineers		165	41.5	-74.85	27.01.10	29.01.10

Source: Various sites of share broking companies

From the above table it is clear that out of 87 IPOs under study which came in the year 2009 and the year 2010, 73 IPOs are trading below their offer price as on 20.07.2012 which is indicated by negative signs in the above table. By analyzing the above data we come to the conclusion that the offer price fixed by the companies was generally high. The above prices of stocks are taken as on week ending 20th July, 2012 when index was very high, SENSEX closes at 17158 and NIFTY at 5205. When the SENSEX was below 17000 and NIFTY was below 5200, many more stocks were traded below their offer price.

IPO MARKET IN 2011

The long-drawn-out flaw in the capital market has wiped out around Rs 4,000 crore of the wealth of investors in the IPO market in 2011. The IPO market has been a big 'wealth destroyer' with 30 IPOs out of 38 IPOs that came during 2011 trading below their issue prices. According to SMC Global Securities, the total amount raised during the year 2011 through public issues was to the tune of about Rs 14112 crore. As markets have rigorously corrected, the current mark-to-market value of these public issues came down to Rs 10014 crore. So, the public issue market of Year 2011 has seen wealth erosion of Rs 4098 crore, representing a mark-to-market loss of 29 %.

IPOS IN 2011

S. No	Company Name	Offer Price (Rs.)	Current Price (Rs) as on 20.07.2011	% Change (+/-)	Issue Dates	Closing Date
1	Aanjanaya Lifecare Ltd	234	525.00	124.36	9-05-11	12-05-11
2	Acropetal Technologies Ltd	90	13.65	-84.83	21-02-11	24-02-11
3	Bharatiya Global Infomedia Ltd	82	6.29	-92.33	11-07-11	14-07-11
4	Birla Pacific Medspa Ltd	10	4.40	-56.00	20-06-11	23-06-11
5	Brooks Laboratories Ltd	100	18.95	-81.05	16-08-11	18-08-11
6	C Mahindra Exports	110	99.90	-9.18	31-12-10	6-01-11
7	Finotex Chemical	70	29.55	-57.79	23-02-11	25-02-11

	Ltd					
8	Flexituf Internation al Ltd.	155	212.15	36.87	29-09-11	5-10-11
9	Future Ventures India Ltd.	10	8.55	-14.50	25-04-11	28-04-11
10	Indo Thai Securities	74	10.15	-86.28	30-09-11	5-10-11
11	Innovative Industries Ltd	117	119.65	2.26	26-04-11	29-04-11
12	Inventure Growth & Securities Ltd.	117	29.95	-74.40	20-07-11	22-07-11
13	L & T Finance Holdings Ltd.	52	46.00	-11.54	27-07-11	29-07-11
14	Lovable Lingeries Ltd	205	329.95	60.95	8-03-11	11-03-11
15	M & B Switchgears Ltd.	186	114.60	-38.39	28-09-11	5-10-11
16	Midvalley Entertainment Ltd.	70	7.11	-89.84	10-01-11	12-01-11
17	Muthoot Finance Ltd	175	131.80	-24.69	18-04-11	21-04-11
18	Omkar Speciality Chemicals Ltd.	98	76.45	-21.99	24-01-11	27-01-11
19	Onelife Capital Advisors	110	489.80	345.27	28-09-11	4-10-11
20	Paramount Printpackaging Ltd.	35	6.34	-81.89	20-04-11	25-04-11

21	PG Electroplast Ltd.	210	154.45	-26.45	7-09-11	12-09-11
22	Prakash Constrowell Ltd.	138	94.20	-31.74	19-09-11	21-09-11
23	PTC India Financial Services Ltd.	27	14.15	-47.59	16-03-11	18-03-11
24	RDB Rasayans Ltd	79	13.66	-82.71	21-09-11	23-09-11
25	Readymade Steel India Ltd	108	74.60	-30.93	27-06-11	29-06-11
26	Rushil Décor Ltd	72	215.15	198.82	20-06-11	23-06-11
27	Sanghvi Forging & Engineering Ltd.	85	64.90	-23.65	4-05-11	9-05-11
28	Servalakshmi Paper Ltd	29	4.65	-83.97	27-04-11	29-04-11
29	Shilpi Cable Technologies Ltd.	69	20.60	-70.14	22-03-11	25-03-11
30	SRS Ltd.	58	40.50	-30.17	23-08-11	26-08-11
31	Sudar Garments Ltd.	77	68.75	-10.71	21-02-11	24-02-11
32	Taksheel Solutions Ltd.	150	11.39	-92.41	29-09-11	4-10-11
33	TD Power System Ltd.	256	280.00	9.38	24-08-11	26-08-11
34	Tijara Polypipes Ltd.	60	7.20	-88.00	27-09-11	29-09-11
35	Timber Home Ltd.	63	36.05	-42.78	30-05-11	2-06-11

36	Tree House Education & Accessories	129	217.40	68.53	10-08-11	12-08-11
37	Vaswani Industries Ltd.	49	6.44	-86.86	29-04-11	3-05-11
38	VMS Industries Ltd.	40	34.10	-14.75	30-05-11	2-06-11

Source: Various sites of share broking companies

Year 2011 has been a particularly bad year for Indian IPOs, and we see that out of the 38 IPOs under study which came in the year 2011, 30 IPOs are trading below their offer price as on 20.07.2012 which is indicated by negative signs in the above table. By analyzing the above data we come to the conclusion that the offer price fixed by the companies was generally high. The above prices of stocks are taken on week ending 20th July, 2012 when index was very high, SENSEX closes at 17158 and NIFTY at 5205. When the SENSEX was below 17000 and NIFTY was below 5200, many more stocks were traded below their offer price. The IPO state of affairs has been going horrific for some time now, and low quality issues combined with a punting mentality has rendered this market completely hopeless for investors.

WHO DECIDES THE PRICE BAND FOR IPO

Company with help of lead managers (merchant bankers or syndicate members) decides the price or price band of an IPO. SEBI, the regulatory authority in India or Stock Exchanges do not play any role in fixing the price of a public issue. SEBI just validate the content of the IPO prospectus. Companies and lead managers do lots of market research and road shows before they decide the appropriate price for the IPO. Companies carry a high risk of IPO failure if they ask for higher premium. Many a time investors do not like the company or the issue price and doesn't apply for it, resulting unsubscribe or undersubscribed issue. In this case companies' either revises the issue price or suspends the IPO.

WHY IPOs ARE PROFITABLE?

Public issues provide you with an opportunity for picking up shares at relatively low prices. Newly formed companies usually offer their shares for subscription at par values, whereas existing companies price their new issues at levels which are sometimes as much as 20 to 30 per cent lower than the market price of their existing shares. For example, new issues priced at Rs. 12 to Rs. 15 per share may be quoted as high as Rs. 20 to Rs. 25 per share in the secondary market soon after their listing on the bourses. Similarly, shares issued at par by new companies also quote at high premiums soon after they get listed on the stock exchange. For example, in early 2004 public issues of Maruti Udyog, Indraprastha Gas and Divi's Labs listed at high premiums. Equally, most companies, which went in for IPOs in 2005 and 2006 did well. In most cases, the initial days after listing saw the stock prices moving well above the listing prices before settling down in a price range. Many companies, which listed during this period gave double digit returns, some companies like Indiabulls, Bharati Shipyard, India Infoline, PTC

India Limited, Shoppers Stop, Sun TV Limited, Suzlon Energy and Tulip IT Services even gave triple digit returns. This is the main reason why public issues are so popular with investors; they offer opportunities for making quick money which few other forms of investment can hope to match, match particularly during the market's bull phase.

REASONS FOR GOING PUBLIC

The company goes for initial public offer keeping the following objectives in mind:

- To raise funds for financing capital expenditure needs like expansion, diversification etc.
- To finance increased working capital requirement
- As an exit route for existing investors
- For debt financing
- To provide a venue for trading the company's shares
- Increase brand name
- To finance possible acquisitions
- To take up new projects
- To execute long-range business models
- To enable its existing shareholders to diversify their investments and to crystallize their capital gains from backing the company – an important consideration for venture capitalists
- By converting to corporate status, a company can always dip back into the market and offer additional shares through a rights issue

IPO NORMS

A number of initiatives were taken to further rationalize the Initial Public Offer (IPO) norms:

- SEBI (Disclosure and Investor Protection) Guidelines require a minimum offering of 25 percent of post issue capital to public. This requirement was relaxed to 10 percent, first for companies in the Information Technology sector, and then in the entertainment, media and telecom sectors.
- In December 2000, this relaxation was extended to companies in all sectors. SEBI also kept the minimum offering size at Rs.100 crore and retained the existing limit of minimum public offer of 20 lakh shares. Companies not meeting the prescribed conditions need to make a minimum public offering of 25 percent.

- With a view to enhancing the quality of issues in the primary market, SEBI tightened the entry norms for IPOs. Accordingly, IPOs of issue size upto 5 times the pre-issue net worth shall be allowed only if the company has track record of profitability and net worth as specified in the Guidelines.
- The book building route has been made compulsory for companies, which do not have such track record. Further, 60 percent of the offer made by them should be allotted to Qualified Institutional Buyers (QIBs) comprising financial institutions, banks, mutual funds, FIIs and VCFs registered with SEBI. Inability to meet this condition would mean failure of the issue.
- The book- building route has also been made compulsory for IPOs with issue size more than 5 times the pre-issue net worth and for public issues by listed companies worth more than 5 times the pre-issue net worth. In these cases also, success of the issue requires allocation of 60 percent of the offer to QIBs.
- The lock-in provisions applicable to IPOs have been rationalised. While the lock-in period for minimum promoters' contribution of 20 percent shall continue to be 3 years, the balance of the entire pre- IPO capital held by promoters or others shall be locked in for 1 year from the date of allotment of the IPO.
- It has also been decided to lock in the shares issued on preferential basis by a listed company to any person for one year from the date of their allotment except in respect of issues involving share swap for acquisition.
- The procedures for allotment of shares and refunds were streamlined. The time for finalizing the allotment has been reduced from 30 to 15 days in book-built issues so as to minimize the risk arising from volatility.

IPO GRADING

IPO Grades are assigned for instance ICRA grading, on a five-point point scale, where IPO Grade 5 indicates the highest grading and IPO Grade 1 indicates the lowest grading, i.e. a higher score indicates stronger fundamentals. An IPO Grade is not an opinion on the price of the issue, pre- or post-listing. An investor in a hitherto unlisted company may either have limited access to information on it, or may find it challenging to appropriately assess, on the basis of the information available, its business prospects and risks. An IPO Grade provides an additional input to investors, in arriving at an investment decision based on independent and objective analysis. In recent times, with the stock market participation of new and foreign investors increasing, there is need for greater value-added information on companies tapping the capital market and their intrinsic quality. In this context, IPO Grades, being simple, objective indicators of the relative fundamental positions of the issuers concerned, could help in both widening and deepening the market.

The highlights of IPO grading are:

- IPO grading is a service aimed at facilitating the assessment of equity issues offered to public and is mandatory as per SEBI guidelines
 - Aimed at providing an independent assessment of fundamentals to aid comparative assessment
 - Intended to serve as an Information and Investment tool for investors
- IPO grading does not take cognizance of the price of the security. It is not an investment recommendation.
- IPO Grading is required prior to marketing of the IPO and needs to be disclosed in the Red Herring Prospectus and Prospectus
- IPO Grading process involves a review of the company background, corporate governance, business, financial performance and SEBI observations

Perceived as the quality gauge for public issues, grading of initial public offers (IPOs) has failed to make a major impact either on the investment rationale of retail investors, or the wealth created by the underlying companies post-listing. In fact, the higher the grade of an IPO, the poorer has been its performance in the market. Companies such as Reliance Power, Edelweiss Capital and Gammon Infrastructure, which were rated four out of five (meaning above average fundamentals), have posted losses in the range of 46 to 56 per cent. And, nine out of 10 which were similarly graded lost more than 40 per cent, according to a report from SMC Capitals.

During 2007 and 2008, the boom years for IPOs, investors hardly took cognizance of ratings assigned to a particular company. And that was the reason why some of the companies with even absolutely low ratings managed to gather stellar subscription figures. Despite opposition from several quarters, the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) had made it mandatory for all IPOs to be graded by rating agencies from April 2007 onwards. After a company gets SEBI approval for an IPO, it has to rope in rating agencies such as ICRA, CRISIL, FITCH and CARE to get the issue graded

ADVANTAGES OF GOING PUBLIC

The going public offers lots of advantages to the company as well as to the investors. The important ones are:

- **STOCK HOLDER DIVERSIFICATION:** As a company grows and becomes more valuable, its founders often have most of its wealth tied up in the company. By selling some of their stock in a public offer, the founders can diversify their holdings and thereby reduce somewhat the risk of their personal portfolios.
- **EASIER TO RAISE NEW CAPITAL:** If a privately held company wants to raise capital a sale of a new stock, it must either go to its existing shareholders or shop

around for other investors. This can often be a difficult and sometimes impossible process. By going public it becomes easier to find new investors for the business.

- **ENHANCE LIQUIDITY:** The stock of a closely held firm has no liquidity. If one of the holders wants to sell some of his shares, it is hard to find potential buyers- especially if the sum involved is large. Even if a buyer is located there is no establishes price at which to complete the transaction. These problems are easily overcome in a publicly owned company.
- **ESTABLISHES VALUE FOR THE FIRM:** This can be very useful in attracting key employees with stock options because the underlying stock have a market value and a market for them to be traded that allows for liquidity for them.
- **IMAGE:** The reputation and visibility of the company increases. It helps to increase company and personal prestige.
- **NO COST OF CAPITAL:** The Company will not pay any interest on the capital raised from public in the form of an IPO. Even it doesn't need to repay the capital. Only in case of liquidation/bankruptcy it needs to pay the residual amount after paying bank loans, debentures, preferential shares etc.
- **HUGE AMOUNTS CAN BE RAISED:** It can raise huge amount of capital by going to public which may not be possible otherwise.
- **DEBT SWAP:** IPOs are one of the ways to rotate debt, which means a company can use funds generated through an IPO to pay off expensive loans. By doing this, companies can reduce the debt burden, thereby, bringing about a balance in the debt-equity ratio.
- **DRIVING PROFESSIONALISM:** An IPO mandates certain standards of performance and compliance. This strengthens professionalism and regulatory awareness among companies. IPOs are a better route to raise funds, especially for SMEs and new entrants
- **CORRECT VALUATION:** Since the share price reflects the company's financial healthiness it would become easy to arrive at a price in case of mergers and acquisitions

DISADVANTAGES OF GOING PUBLIC

Going public also offers certain disadvantages such as:

- **COST OF REPORTING:** A publicly owned company must file quarterly reports with the Securities and exchange Board of India. These reports can be costly especially for small firms.

- **DISCLOSURE OF INFORMATION:** Once a company becomes public it has to disclose so much information to public on regular intervals. This includes share holding pattern, quarterly and annual financial statements, profiles of directors etc. Because of this restriction companies will always be under pressure to perform and show profits in every quarter. This, some times, doesn't allow the management to take bold steps which may yield long term benefits but less profits in short term.
- **SELF DEALINGS:** The owner's managers of closely held companies have many opportunities for self-transactions, although legal they may not want to disclose to the public.
- **INACTIVE MARKET LOW PRICE:** If a firm is very small and its shares are not traded frequently, then its stock will not really be liquid and the market price may not be truly representative of the stocks value.
- **CONTROL:** Owning less than 50% of the shares could lead to a loss of control in the management.
- **PROFIT IS DISTRIBUTED:** The profit earned by the company should be shared with its investors in the form of dividend.
- **COSTLY AFFAIR:** An IPO is a costly affair. Around 15-20% of the amount realized is spent on raising the same. Also, a substantial amount of time and effort has to be invest.

PRECAUTIONS TO BE TAKEN WHILE INVESTING IN NEW ISSUES (IPO)

New issues (IPO) can be divided into two broad groups:

- New issues of newly formed companies, and
- New issues of existing companies.

New issues of existing companies are, by and large, very good investments. They provide an opportunity for acquiring shares in ongoing profit-making companies at relatively low prices. On the other hand, all new issues of newly formed companies are not good investments.

Some of the important precautions which should be taken while selecting the right new issues for investment are mentioned herein below:

- Avoid investment in a company having unknown and untried promoters;
- Check the reputation and market standing of the foreign collaborator, if there is one;
- Companies where the foreign collaborator has an equity stake are often considered as good investments;
- Avoid investment in a company, which is not ready to start business operations;

- Invest in companies that have something new to offer;
- Invest in companies that operate in high-growth sectors of the economy;
- Apply for the mega issues of well-known profit-earning companies;

STEPS TO BE TAKEN BY COMPANIES WHILE GOING FOR AN IPO

It is to be taken into account that going for an IPO is definitely not easy. The right recipe is to go step by step cautiously with each step dependent on the other. If the company misses out one step, the whole structure will crumble."

Making an IPO involves immense research, planning and strategizing. So, an error even on a miniscule level can have drastic repercussions. The following steps are noteworthy:

- **CHOOSING THE PERFECT TIME:** The timing of going public is very crucial in the pre-IPO process. One should look into many aspects before the plunge—like looking into the prevailing market sentiment. In the 1980's and early 1990's when branding and marketing were non-existent, liquidity in the market, behaviour of the secondary market and merchant bankers' advice were instrumental in deciding the right time for the IPO.
- **CHOOSING THE RIGHT TEAM:** Apart from the CEO or the Chairman, the main members are the CFO, COO, the Company Secretary, the auditors, professional merchant bankers, and the CIO in the current age of information and legal advisors. Only an intelligent team can contribute to the success of the venture. Team building and the professional team that a company brings in is very important. The company should be very careful not only about land and equipment but also while deploying money and manpower.
- **DEFINITE GOALS AND PURPOSES:** A company should be focused and clear about the purpose of the IPO. Usually, the purpose behind companies making an IPO is to accumulate funds and finances for expansion and investments and above all woo the investors and consolidate as a brand. This requires a purely corporate structure. Currently, there are stringent SEBI guidelines to be followed before any company goes public. Keeping this in mind, the valuations which the company wishes to command will depend on the future goals and projects of the company, and the management team. Unless the management is fully sure of the ultimate goals, the company will not be able to come up with a high valuation for the proposed issue of shares.
- **CHOOSING THE RIGHT MERCHANT BANKERS:** The primary role of a merchant banker should be to act as a bridge between the organization and the investors. Firstly, the merchant banker should have a brand image in the market. He should have sound knowledge of the capital market and about the industry in which the company operates. A merchant banker should have the capability and the experience to handle a large-scale IPO. And they should be able to reach a larger mass of people because investors today are just not located in the metros but also in tier-II and tier-III cities. The merchant

bankers will communicate the future projects and growth prospects of the organisation to the investors. Simultaneously, they also chalk out the risk management strategies for the company since risks and ventures are two sides of the same coin.

- **CAPITAL RESTRUCTURING:** Companies should decide on the ways to deploy their capital, namely capital restructuring. Companies should be clear about the debt and equity ratio. This brings down to setting the ideal Debt-Equity Ratio, which can vary from 1:1 to 2:1. The way companies are going to deploy their capital is also very important. Companies have to be very careful while deploying the resources and forecast the profit they will incur in three-four years' time. Also when it comes to capital restructuring, a company should be focused and clear about the proportion of the management and the stakes they are willing to dilute to the public.
- **CREATING INVESTOR INTEREST:** Confidence building and generating investor interest should be on the priority list for a company. A company must project an image of transparency and good governance to the investors. Infosys should be the role model for all companies going in for an IPO. Many of the experts agree that IT giant Infosys is a role model because their balance sheet is very clear, they value their managers as assets and year after year they expand rapidly. A company is accountable to its investors, which is why when they go public they have to disclose company projections—past, present and future prospects.
- **MEDIA CAMPAIGNS:** A few years ago, marketing and media campaigns were considered a luxury, but today they are absolutely necessary. They contribute to the relative success of an IPO venture. The campaigns can be in the form of road shows and extensive investor meetings. They are required because the investors need to be made aware of the company and its past performances and any important projects undertaken/completed. During the campaigns, various facets related to company performance, the need to raise money and future plans are disclosed, information that investors seek. A successful media campaign ensures complete participation in the IPO by one and all.

IPO FAILURE

The gross and continuous failure of issues to attract retail subscriptions has started ringing alarm bells among decision makers. If this continues, the government's disinvestment programme will be badly affected. Poor retail participation is the result of years of poor regulation and malpractices by market participants, which have caused equity products to perform very poorly.

The issuers (entities coming out with public offers) don't want to leave money on the table. They want to maximize the price. The companies need to have a heart to give money and let others make money.

Every IPO appears to be over-priced against its listed peers. For IPO, there is no comparable track record on the return on capital. So a company currently serving 10 Crore capital could be having EPS of Rs 12. But the moment it launches public issue to raise the capital to 20 Crore,

makes it's EPS to Rs 6. And we do not have data at the point of IPO on how they have served the 20 Crore Capital. So these companies have benefit of data absence due to which SEBI may not be able to stop them from even asking for Price to current Earning ratio of 100, if they overstate their estimated earnings. There is another angle. Even the listed companies, e.g in Infrastructure Development, have meagre EPS, but they are valued at 40 plus times. But their assets real value could be very high, leading to higher stock pricing.

At any point of time PE ratio more than 10 times is absolute madness; but behind the India growth story everything is being over priced. Even now many of the IPOs and Shares are at about PE ratio of 18, it clearly shows that market is over priced and in long run there will be correction. Having high expectations is not regulated, therefore these IPOs are overpriced. Investor has to think what his expected return is and exit timing.

It is a fact that IPO's of recent times were & are overpriced. The economic advisors have gone wrong in reading the mood of the primary investors. The investors are now looking forward to secondary markets, due to the fact that they are now advised by Asset Managers-who are increasing their numbers.

NHPC: After Adani Power, NHPC proved to be yet another disappointing issue for those hopeful for quick gains. The company failed to deliver spectacular listing gains that many retail investors expected and closed with a gain of 2%.

JSW ENERGY: Retail investors stayed aloof from the JSW Energy initial public offering (IPO) despite the discount of Rs. 5 on the issue price. The issue has been fully subscribed. According to data available on the exchanges, the retail portion was subscribed only 0.4 times. The price band for the Rs. 2,700-crore issue was fixed at Rs. 100-115. Merchant bankers close to the issue said that retail investors are still apprehensive about IPOs, especially those from the power sector. The entire power sector IPOs of 2009 are trading at a discount to their issue prices. Due to this retail investors were wary of this issue too. Though the Reliance Power IPO witnessed huge investor interest and was fully subscribed within first few minutes of its book building process, it could not sustain the momentum in first day's listing and dipped below its issue price.

SUGGESTIONS

After going through the study we present the following suggestions:

- The IPO pricing exercise needs to strike a fine balance between the following conflicting objectives - optimally monetizing the issuer's holdings and achieving high valuations for the stock, making the attractive from the investor's standpoint and after-market performance because "Pricing is the key,". In order to provide good returns to the investors, companies should fix their prices fairly, neither under pricing nor over pricing.
- Reasonable premium should be charged on the shares otherwise prices will not represent the fair valuation.
- In many ways, marketing an IPO is akin to marketing a movie or an FMCG product, such as a cola or a pizza. These days, IPOs need a touch of brand marketing and management

involving well-placed positioning and correct pricing. Following that, the company needs to wait for investors to bite the bait. Just as FMCG companies stimulate the customers to drink and consume their products, a company issuing an IPO should also excite the investors to 'consume' the IPO. If branding, timing, pricing and communication are not correct, the IPO will be lost.

- Full disclosures should be made by the company in the offer document so that investors may make proper analysis before investing.
- Companies should adhere to the IPO norms set up by various authorities such as SEBI.

CONCLUSION

We know that Indian share market tops the hot list of all the investors whether domestic or global but the smartness of watchdog SEBI and fund raisers lies in passing on the premium benefit to retail domestic investors and increasing their involvement which at present is a meager 10%. With further liberalization and increased monitoring we can expect a better future for retailers in the market. Pulling down QIB on same platform as retailers is one of the major initiatives of the year which is proposed by SEBI. If all these proposals get through, there is no doubt that the participation of retail investors may see a rise in market.

The IPO market is a good setting in which to study the effect of 'irrational' investors on stock prices. IPO firms by definition have no prior share price history and tend to be young, immature, and relatively informational opaque. Not surprisingly, therefore, they are hard to value, and it seems reasonable to assume that investors will have a wide range of priors about their market values. Secondary markets out performed primary markets in 2009, but we expect 2012 and 2013 will be exciting performance for both primary and secondary markets

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